

Reduction of Symmetrical Dichloracetone by Yeast.

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It was found by one of us (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 1) that unsymmetrical dichloracetone lends itself to easy reduction by yeast, whereas monochloracetone gave very indifferent results, acting poisonously towards yeast even in weak concentrations. It was, therefore, considered desirable to extend this yeast reduction process to some other chlorinated ketones,¹ as the inhibiting influence of these upon yeast would probably furnish at least a qualitative measure of their physiological activity. Attempts are being made to regulate the addition of chlorinated ketones to the fermenting sugar solution with the help of an electric potential recorder first described by Potter (*Proc Royal Society*, 1911, B, 84, 260), so that the influence of inhibition due to concentration may be as near as possible measured or eliminated and useful light thrown on the mechanism of the

¹ We notice that the biochemical reduction of chlorinated ketones, although for the first time introduced by one of us, has been undertaken by another worker (Pietro Santomauro, *Biochem Zeit*, 1924, 151, 48) without even the customary references, to which we draw the attention of colleagues

3-carbon theory of alcoholic fermentation. Besides, the use of chlorinated secondary alcohols or their urethane derivatives as hypnotics suggested by one of us (*loc. cit.*), gives additional interest to biochemical reduction processes of the said nature. The experiments further point to the important function which the enzyme 'reductase' plays in general alcoholic fermentation, and from which a connected chemical representation of the process of alcoholic fermentation has been attempted.*

EXPERIMENTAL.

Symmetrical dichloracetone $\text{CH}_2\text{Cl.CO.CH}_2\text{Cl}$ was prepared by the oxidation of dichlorhydrin (symmetrical dichlorisopropyl alcohol). The obtaining of pure dichlorhydrin in any quantity, which is an industrial product of some importance, was rather difficult, and the yield stated to have been obtained by Carius (*Annalen*, 168, 43) could in no case be attained, a little more than half of the recorded yield being available. Using 150 grams pure glycerine and 375 grams of Merck's sulphur chloride (freshly distilled before use), only 62 grams of dichlorhydrin was obtained which collected mostly at 178°C and corresponded to 42% of the theory. The purity of the alcohol was established by preparing the known urethane derivative which melted at $80\text{-}81^\circ\text{C}$.

The method of preparing symmetrical dichloracetone which is described in *Annalen* (208, 353) giving a very poor yield, was modified as follows:—

25 grams of dichlorhydrin was taken in a 250 c.c. stoppered bottle and 20 grams of finely powdered (120 mesh) potassium dichromate were added to it and mixed well. 30 grams of concentrated sulphuric acid diluted with 30 c.c. of water and cooled, were then added

* The paper was read before the Chemical Section of the Indian Science Congress, at its sitting in Benares (1925)

to the mixture little by little during about $2\frac{1}{2}$ hours, the bottle being kept cool in ice and shaken from time to time. In the addition of the acid, care was taken that no evolution of gas took place, as this leads to further oxidation of the ketone. It was observed that the reduction of the dichromate took place very slowly in the cold, as shown by the colour of the mixture, which was, therefore, allowed to stand after addition of the total quantity of acid, at room temperature (25°C) for a quarter of an hour, and shaken repeatedly. The oxidation proceeded and the solution showed a tendency to warm up and liberate gas. The bottle was then quickly replaced in ice water and the reaction mitigated. The oxidation was brought to completion in this way, and the mixture finally slightly warmed up on the water-bath. It was cooled, extracted with ether, the ethereal solution well shaken up with a freshly prepared strong solution of sodium bisulphite when all the ketone went into the aqueous layer, leaving the unconverted dichlorhydrin dissolved in the ethereal layer. The aqueous layer was separated, decomposed with dilute sulphuric acid and distilled, the ketone, being volatile in steam, distilled over with the aqueous distillate, which was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate, the ether evaporated and the residual oil fractionated. An oily liquid distilling at 172°C was collected, which mostly solidified into a beautiful crystalline mass in the condenser, and was symmetrical dichloracetone. The crystals melting at 45°C have a pungent and tear-bringing odour. The yield amounted to 6 grams.

The reduction of symmetrical dichloracetone was conducted in the same way as in the case of unsymmetrical dichloracetone described before (*loc. cit.*). 250 grams of cane sugar dissolved in 2.5 litres of tap

water to which sufficient fresh yeast was added, were slowly treated with a 25% alcoholic solution of symmetrical dichloroacetone, soon after brisk fermentation had commenced. Nine grams of the chloro-ketone were added in 4 hours, and the mixture allowed to ferment overnight. Next day in order to ensure complete fermentation of sugar, 100 grams of pressed yeast were further added, and the mixture allowed to stand for two days with occasional shaking. The clear liquid was next decanted and distilled under reduced pressure. The residue after decantation was washed two or three times with water and the aqueous extract distilled under reduced pressure as usual. The total distillate which amounted to about 2.8 litres was extracted with two pounds of ether, the ethereal solution dried over ignited sodium sulphate, and the ether expelled on the water-bath. Five c.c. of an oily liquid remained behind, which when fractionated gave 4.8 grams of a clear liquid boiling at 178°C, and identical with dichlorhydrin.

The urethane derivative, already known (Otto, *J. pr. Chem.*, [2], 44, 20) and patented under the name, *aleudrin* (Mass, *Biochem. Zeit.*, 143, 65) was prepared as follows:—

Equimolecular proportions of chloroformamide and symmetrical dichloroacetone were dissolved separately in dry ether and the two mixed in the cold. The mixture was allowed to stand at the room temperature for fifteen minutes, and then heated on the water-bath to expel all the ether. The residue was treated with water to decompose any remaining chloroformamide and to dissolve out the solid ammonium chloride. The oily mass on scratching soon set into a white crystalline solid which when recrystallised from alcohol, melted at 80-81°C. A mixture of this with the urethane compound from the original dichlorhydrin also melted at 80-81°C.

If, however, an excess of chloroformamide (two molecular proportion to one of dichlorhydrin) be employed, the allophanic ester is produced :—

This compound melts at 182°C. The crude product, however, seemed to be never free from the urethane derivative, as after crystallising the allophanic ester from hot 60% alcohol, the mother-liquor when cooled with ice gave a fresh crop of crystals which did not melt sharply.

Found: N=13·14; Cl=32·56. $\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{O}_3\text{N}_2\text{Cl}_2$ requires N=13·02 and Cl=33·02 per cent.

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